
A CASE STUDY ON VIRTUAL TVET FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY SYSTEMS IN MYANMAR

Suresh K. Dhameja, Naeem Yaqoob, Heidi Uy, Arlene Monge, Stephanie Rimas
Colombo Plan Staff College, Philippines

Abstract

The transition to renewable energy is a critical global priority in addressing climate change, yet countries such as Myanmar face challenges in developing a skilled workforce to support this transition. This study examines the implementation of Virtual Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) for renewable energy systems in Myanmar. Data were collected from the 10 participants of the Colombo Plan Staff College's Training of Trainers program conducted online in December 2025. Findings indicate that Virtual TVET leverages digital platforms, interactive modules, and online simulations to teach practical competencies in solar, hydropower, and biomass energy systems. While participants reported enhanced technical skills and accessibility, challenges remain in instructor capacity, digital infrastructure, and consistent program adoption. Opportunities for scaling Virtual TVET and integrating best practices are discussed to guide future workforce development initiatives in Myanmar's renewable energy sector.

Key Words: Renewable Energy, Virtual TVET, Workforce Development, Digital Learning, Myanmar

1. INTRODUCTION

The recently concluded United Nations Climate Change Conference (UN COP 30) last November 2025 in Belém, Brazil brought forth once again the ongoing discussion about the mobilization of national climate action plans to address the perennial issue of climate change. Part of this initiative is transitioning from using fossil fuels to triple renewable energy as we double energy efficiency by 2030 in countries across the world. The aim is to maintain the global temperature rise below 2°C and limit it to 1.5°C celsius (European Commission, 2025). The latest conference highlighted the importance of coordinated action among countries in order to accomplish these targets while ensuring a just and equitable transition for all regions (International Institute for Sustainable Development, 2025).

Since 1992, the United Nations has effectively facilitated negotiations in producing notable accords to combat the global temperature rise. The creation of the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) has set the tone in the crusade for environmental preservation by preventing dangerous human interference in the climate system. From there, several more conferences were conducted by the organization to continuously monitor the persisting case of climate change. The turning point for the UN COP came with the signing of the global climate change agreement better known as the Paris Agreement. One hundred and six countries (106) both developed and developing nations, took part in this

monumental event. These nations pledged to set emissions reduction goals with nationally determined contributions (NDCs) as the depicted targets (UNFCCC, 2015).

Ten years after the Paris Agreement, the global lenses are now focused on efforts that will phase out fossil fuels, combat deforestation, and scale up renewable energy deployment (IEA, 2021; IRENA, 2021). The attention is now being shifted towards the transformative approaches to energy production, consumption, and human resource development. With countries transitioning to ambitious energy pathways, the need for a skilled workforce who are capable of supporting renewable energy systems has become a critical enabling factor (IEA, 2021; IRENA, 2021).

The Asia-Pacific region, specifically Southeast Asia, has been in the frontlines of such global discussion given its heavy reliance on coal and gas. And despite its cultural richness and megabiodiversity, the region has been subjected to the climate impacts due to its strategic yet vulnerable location. Climate impacts such as extreme weather events, sea-level rise, and flooding pose significant threats to socioeconomic development (ADB, 2015; CEEED Philippines, 2025). However, the dual challenge of sustaining economic growth and transitioning to clean energy highlights the urgent need for renewable energy deployment and capacity building initiatives (CARE Climate Change, n.d.).

In Myanmar, efforts have been made to mitigate carbon emissions by 40% with 2018 as the baseline year. This included the expansion of renewable energy as a major policy action (The Republic of the Union of Myanmar, 2021). Hydropower and solar power are some of the renewable energy sources that are found to be abundant and are currently being utilized in the country (Vakulchuk et al., 2017). With this, a power supply plan using renewable energy and a program to attract investors was established by Myanmar to further explore the potential of renewable energy (IGC, 2016; ASEAN Centre for Energy, 2020). Through this initiative, rural households and public institutions were encouraged to utilize renewable energy as the country gathers investors through the National Electrification Project which was funded by the World Bank in 2015 (World Bank, 2015; Government of the Republic of the Union of Myanmar, 2018). However, the rapid growth in the national economy also led to the increase in the electricity demand among its people. The citizens gradually turned to biomass such as firewood and charcoal as the primary source of energy. In return, people suffered from diseases caused by the dust and deforestation became more rampant especially in the rural areas (ADB, 2015; ERIA, 2019).

As Myanmar continues to solve both its electricity problems and alleviate the effects of climate change, another persisting concerns that came into full view were the shortage of skilled personnel, limited training facilities, and uneven access to instructors who are proficient in the utilization of renewable energy (Borgen Project, 2024; CARE Climate Change, n.d.). These constraints underscore the importance of employing innovative approaches specifically in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) which is deemed instrumental in equipping a workforce with the practical skills required for the renewable energy transition.

In this context, TVET institutions have resorted to leveraging digital platforms, online simulations, and Learning Management Systems (LMS) as a form of a strategic solution (ADB, 2021; World Bank, 2020). The concept of Virtual TVET was introduced to allow learners across Myanmar to acquire relevant competencies in renewable energy systems notwithstanding the limitations of physical infrastructure or

the scarcity of qualified instructors. Interactive modules were provided to learners so as to practice technical skills such as solar panel installation, hydropower system maintenance, or biomass energy management. Virtual environments were set up to replicate real-world scenarios, yet the challenge remains on the aspect of ensuring equitable access and consistent adoption across all the Myanmar TVET institutions (UNESCO, 2020).

Hence, this study aims to explore the extent of the implementation of Virtual TVET in the context of renewable energy systems in Myanmar. Specifically, this will delve on how digital tools are being leveraged by TVET institutions to equip learners with the technical skills necessary for renewable energy deployment. Moreover, opportunities, challenges, and best practices were highlighted to inform more effective adoption strategies, develop learner competencies, and guide future undertakings in integrating Virtual TVET for renewable energy systems across Myanmar.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

This study utilized a single-case exploratory study design to assess the implementation of Virtual Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) for renewable energy systems in Myanmar. This approach provided an in-depth exploration of a contemporary phenomenon within the real-life context (Yin, 2018). Institutional practices, learner engagement, and integration of digital tools were examined to capture the complexities and nuances of the Virtual TVET adoption in the renewable energy sector. The data were collected from the participants of the *Training of Trainers on Renewable Energy System Using Virtual TVET Online In-Country Program* (ICP) that was conducted by the Colombo Plan Staff College (CPSC) in December 2025. The data were collected from 10 program participants who provided insights into the institutional practices, learner engagement, and digital tool utilization, respectively. Though the sample size is small, this allowed for a focused and in-depth exploration of the case as it captures practical challenges, opportunities, and best practices in the implementation of Virtual TVET specifically in the renewable energy sector.

2.2 Study Context

Despite its rigorous effort to fully utilize the high potential for renewable energy, Myanmar continues to face challenges in capacitating its skilled workforce due to its limited access to formal TVET infrastructure, trained instructors, and practical training facilities (ILO, 2014; UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018). Such situations are more felt in rural and underserved regions due to insufficient electrical supply and uneven technical education (World Bank, 2015).

Given the gravity of these circumstances, the Virtual TVET has emerged as a pragmatic and adaptive response to Myanmar's structural challenges and geographic constraints (UNESCO, 2020; ADB, 2021). With Virtual TVET, the delivery of renewable energy training goes beyond the traditional confines of physical institutions and regular classroom settings. This training modality makes use of digital platforms, online simulations, and Learning Management Systems (World Bank, 2020).

Premising from the Training of Trainers on Renewable Energy Systems Using Virtual TVET Online In-Country Program conducted by the Colombo Plan Staff College (CPSC), this study is aimed at enhancing the competencies of TVET practitioners who are involved in renewable energy education while assessing the feasibility and effectiveness of the virtual training approach under Myanmar's prevailing conditions.

Instead of seeking statistical generalization, this case study focuses on analytical depth and contextual understanding of how Virtual TVET is presently implemented, experienced, and perceived by the ICP participants. The insights that were generated from this context provided a grounded understanding of the opportunities, constraints, and practical considerations that are associated with the deployment of Virtual TVET.

2.3 Data Sources

This study drew on multiple sources of evidence so as to support an in-depth case study analysis of the Virtual TVET implementation for renewable energy systems in Myanmar:

- **Primary data:** A structured survey was administered to the participants of the Training of Trainers on Renewable Energy Systems Using Virtual TVET Online In-Country Program last December 2025. The survey captured the participants' demographics, and gathered their insights on the following key areas: the effectiveness of digital and virtual TVET integration in their institutions, observed skill gaps among learners, the use of digital tools and innovative practices in teaching, and challenges encountered in implementing Virtual TVET. The respondents also shared their perspectives on strategies that will strengthen their country's and institutions' digital TVET skills and programs. A total of ten (10) respondents completed the survey, all of whom held training-related or TVET delivery roles within their respective TVET institutions.
- **Secondary data:** The secondary data were gathered from program-related documents including training materials, instructional guides, and institutional reports (Ministry of Education, 2016; UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018). These sources provided context on the design, delivery, and structure of the Virtual TVET program. Moreover, relevant policy documents such as national TVET strategies, renewable energy policies, and digital learning frameworks were reviewed to examine the extent to which existing policies support and enable Virtual TVET adoption in Myanmar (Republic of the Union of Myanmar, 2014; Republic of the Union of Myanmar, 2016-2021).

3. SAMPLING AND DATA COLLECTION

This study utilized a purposive sampling method in which the respondents were selected through their direct involvement in TVET delivery, digital learning, or renewable energy training within Myanmar. The respondents were also participants of the Training of Trainers on Renewable Energy Systems Using Virtual TVET Online which is an In-Country Program conducted by CPSC.

By actively engaging these individuals who are specifically involved in training and instructional roles in their respective TVET institutions, the researchers were able to capture informed insights about the adoption and challenges of Virtual TVET in the renewable energy context.

The following are the demographic profiles of the respondents who participated in study.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Survey Respondents (n=10)

Variable	Categories	Frequency
Gender	Female	9
	Male	1
Age	30-39	3
	40-49	6
	50 +	1
Designation	Assistant Lecturer	1
	Associate Professor	1
	Deputy Director	1
	EP	1
	ME (EP)	1
	Lecturer	5
Institution	Department of Technical and Vocational Education (DTVE)	1
	DTVE / Government Technical Institute (GTI), Taunggyi	1
	Department of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (DTVET)	1
	Government Technical Institute, Mawlamyine (GTI Mawlamyine)	1

	Government Technical Institute, Yamethin (GTI Yamethin)	1
	Government Technical Institute, Magway (GTI Magway)	1
	Government Technical Institute, Yenangyaung (GTI Yenangyaung)	1
	Technical and Vocational Education and Training, GTHS Ywa Ma (TVET, GTHS Ywa Ma)	1
	Technical and Vocational Education and Training, GTI Insein (TVET, GTI Insein)	1
	Technical and Vocational Education and Training / Government Technical Institute, Thanlyin (TVET/GTI Thanlyin)	1

A total of ten (10) participants successfully completed the structured online survey. Though small in terms of number, the sample size reflects the exploratory and in-depth nature of this case study. This emphasized the analytical richness of the topic over statistical generalization. The responses were collected directly from the participants to ensure accurate representation of their experiences, perceptions, and challenges in terms of the implementation of Virtual TVET in their respective institutions. This approach created a focused examination of the practical consideration, institutional practices, and opportunities for scaling Virtual TVET within Myanmar.

4. DISCUSSION

This section presents the key findings of the study in relation to the implementation of Virtual TVET for renewable energy systems in Myanmar. Drawing primarily on the result of the online survey, the discussion examines institutional and instructional practices, challenges encountered in the adoption of Virtual TVET, and the perceived gaps in the skills and digital readiness among TVET institutions. These findings are then situated within the broader context of the national policies in order to assess the extent to

which the existing TVET systems, renewable energy, and digital learning policies support or constrain the implementation of the Virtual TVET initiatives in the country (Yin, 2018; UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018).

Table 2. Skills Gap Evident Among Learners in TVET Institutions

Skill Gap	Frequency	% of Respondents
Technical/industry-specific skills (automotive, electrical, HVAC, renewable energy)	9	90
Digital/ICT skills (LMS, virtual learning tools, simulations)	5	50
Soft Skills (communication, teamwork, leadership, interpersonal, etc.)	5	50
Entrepreneurial Skills	3	30
Green Skills	1	10
Adaptive Skills	1	10
Learning to Learn Skills	5	50
Others: Internet Skills	1	10

Table 2 showcases the observed skills gap by the respondents among the learners in their respective institutions. The results indicate that **technical and industry specific skills** were deemed to be the most prominent skills gap as reported by 90% of the respondents. Moreover, **digital and ICT skills, soft skills, and learning-to-learn skills** all garnered 50% of the responses which clearly indicates that learners do not only require technical competencies but also essential digital literacy and transferable skills in order to thrive in modern work environments. Meanwhile, a small yet significant portion of the participants identified **entrepreneurial skills** (30%), **green skills** (10%), **adaptive skills** (10%), and **internet skills** (10%) as evident skills gaps though less widespread as opposed to the previously mentioned (ILO, 2021; IRENA, 2021). However, these are vital for holistic workforce development in the renewable energy sector. Nevertheless, these findings underscore the need for Virtual TVET programs to prioritize practical, industry-aligned technical training while simultaneously integrating digital tools, soft skills development, and adaptive learning approaches.

Table 3: Digital Learning Modules Integrated into Institutions' TVET Programs

Digital Learning Module	Frequency	% of Respondents
Overview of a Digital TVET Framework and Virtual TVET	7	70
Blended Learning using Virtual TVET	4	40
Using a TVET LMS to Deliver Competency-Based	5	50

Training		
TVET LMS Reporting and Analytics	2	20
Technical Operation and Troubleshooting of Modern Training Systems	3	30
Fundamentals of Green and Renewable Energy	4	40
Supporting Systems	1	10
Green Technology System Simulations	2	20
Incorporating Lesson Plans using Virtual TVET	6	60

Table 3 highlights the digital learning modules that are presently integrated into the TVET programs of the participants' institutions. The results illustrate that the majority of the respondents (70%) noted the inclusion of an **overview of a Digital TVET framework and Virtual TVET** which demonstrates that foundational digital training is widely recognized as an essential program component. Likewise, 60% of the respondents **incorporate lesson plans using Virtual TVET** which reflect efforts to embed virtual teaching strategies directly into the curriculum. Modules that focus on **competency-based training through TVET LMS** were reported by 50% of the participants while **blended learning approaches and fundamentals of green and renewable energy** were each identified by 40%. This suggests moderate adoption of these specialized and practical modules in the TVET programs. Technical operation and troubleshooting of modern training systems (30%), TVET LMS reporting and analytics (20%), green technology system simulations (20%), and supporting systems (10%) were found to be less frequently integrated given their required additional resources or capacity building (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018). These outcomes reveal that while core digital TVET frameworks and lesson plan integration are still prioritized, the variable adoption of advanced, technical, and green-focused modules exposes both infrastructural and human resources constraints.

Table 4. Innovative Practices or Programs Promoting Digital TVET Learning in Institutions

Innovative Practice/Program	Frequency	% of Respondents
Virtual workshops and simulations	7	70
Industry mentorships or internships	5	50
Online project-based activities	2	20
Integration of green and renewable energy simulations	4	40
Digital assessment and certification	6	60

Table 4 reflects the innovative practices and programs that were implemented by the participants' TVET institutions to enhance Digital TVET learning. The results indicate that **virtual workshops and simulations** are the most widely adopted practice as reported by 70% of the respondents. This emphasizes the strong prioritization of experiential learning in a digital environment. This was followed by **digital**

assessment and certification at 60% which shows efforts to formalize and recognize learner competencies achieved through virtual training. **Industry mentorships or internships** were reported by 50% of the participants which demonstrates a moderate level of collaboration with the private sector in providing real-world exposure and skill application. The **integration of green and renewable energy simulations** appears in 40% of the responses from the institutional representatives which points to a growing though not yet widespread initiative on sustainability and sector-specific technical skills. Online project-based activities are deemed to be least adopted (20%) which indicate potential for expanding learner engagement through collaborative and applied digital projects (IRENA, 2022; UNESCO, 2020). These findings highlight the TVET institutions' prioritization of practical, simulation-based learning and digital credentialing. Nevertheless, opportunities to further incorporate industry partnerships, project-based activities, and renewable energy-focused innovation can be explored to strengthen Virtual TVET outcomes (ILO, 2014).

Table 5. Challenges Affecting Virtual TVET Adoption in Myanmar

Challenge	Frequency	% of Respondents
Limited or unreliable internet connectivity	7	70
Lack of access to devices for students or trainers	5	50
Insufficient knowledge of LMS platforms among trainers	6	60
Difficulty in assessing competency-based learning online	2	20
Weak engagement of learners in virtual/blended learning	3	30
Policy or regulatory barriers for online TVET programs	2	20

Table 5 reveals the main challenges that were faced by TVET institutions in adopting Virtual TVET in Myanmar. The most frequently occurring challenge as reported by the respondents is the **limited or unreliable internet connectivity** as cited by 70% of the participants. This exposes the critical role of stable digital infrastructure in enabling virtual learning. Moreover, **insufficient knowledge of LMS platforms among trainers** comes in second with 60% response rate which highlights the need for an enhanced faculty capacity-building in digital teaching tools. 50% of the respondents reported that **lack of access to devices for students or trainers** affect their institutions which shows both infrastructural and resource constraints that limit equitable participation in Virtual TVET programs. Weak engagement of learners (30%), difficulty in assessing competency-based learning online (20%), and policy or regulatory barriers for online TVET programs (20%) were seen as challenges though less frequently reported. These findings highlight the barriers in pedagogy, learner motivation, and governance. Overall, it can be deemed from the consolidated data that the primary obstacles to Virtual TVET adoption are technological and capacity-related (ADB, 2021; UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018).

To situate the survey results on Virtual TVET adoption within Myanmar's broader policy environment, it is crucial to examine the relevant national strategies, educational reforms, and sector coordination efforts that influence TVET, digital learning, and workforce development. The National Education Strategic Plan (NESP) 2021-2030 embodies Myanmar's overarching policy framework for education, placing significant

emphasis on modernizing teaching and learning methods, promoting blended and digital learning, and ensuring that TVET and other education pathways respond to the evolving needs of the labour market. The plan's development involved extensive stakeholder consultation, including government officials, educators, and international partners, who highlighted the need to address 21st-century competencies and lifelong learning opportunities for all learners (NESP, 2021–2030).

Within the NESP's strategic components, there is explicit recognition of the importance of digital technologies and infrastructure for education. For example, draft components of the plan include improving ICT technology and enhancing online, offline, and blended teaching and learning, strengthening digital learning management systems, and building national digital connectivity networks linking universities, TVET centres, and other institutions. These components aim to support the integration of digital platforms including Learning Management Systems (LMS) across education sectors, which aligns with the survey findings showing moderate adoption of LMS-based training modules (50%) and foundational digital TVET frameworks (70%).

Moreover, the NESP mentions strategic priorities such as enhancing the continuous professional development of in-service teachers, including digital competencies and pedagogies, as well as establishing national digital infrastructure to support blended teaching and learning. This policy orientation resonates with the survey results, where respondents reported challenges related to limited LMS knowledge among trainers (60%) and limited access to digital infrastructure (50%). These policy interests in teacher capacity building and digital infrastructure suggest an enabling intent; however, the findings illustrate that the operationalization of these policies remains uneven, particularly in rural and underserved regions.

The NESP also reflects broader goals for TVET system strengthening, emphasizing access to TVET for diverse population groups, competency-based modular short courses, and enhanced quality and relevance of TVET programming. Specifically, TVET-related strategies call for expanded access, a strengthened governance system, and improved alignment with labor market demands, all of which provide a strategic foundation for addressing the technical and industry-specific skills gaps identified by 90% of respondents in the current study. Such strategies mirror efforts to build national skills standards and reinforce partnerships between public and private sectors, although policy implementation is still evolving in practice.

Beyond the NESP, multi-stakeholder reviews of the TVET system including reports developed with support from the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) have emphasized the need for enhanced trainer capacity, cooperation with the private sector, and the adoption of digital technologies to modernize TVET delivery and improve relevance to industry needs. These system review reports bolster the policy environment for digital TVET innovation and align with survey respondents' reports of virtual workshops and simulations (70%) and digital assessment and certification (60%). However, the persistence of barriers such as unreliable internet connectivity (70%) and insufficient digital tool access underscore the gap between strategic intent and institutional readiness for effective Virtual TVET implementation.

Finally, Myanmar's broader development policy context, including the *Myanmar Sustainable Development Plan (MSDP) 2018-2030*, underscores the imperative for 21st-century skill development, equitable access to quality education, and labour market alignment across all education subsectors. The MSDP emphasises strengthening teacher recruitment, training, and quality assurance as such that these elements resonate with the learner and trainer capacity issues noted in the survey, and with strategic goals to produce a workforce equipped for a competitive, innovative economy.

Together, these policy frameworks provide an enabling strategic environment that supports concepts central to Virtual TVET such as ICT integration, blended learning, and workforce competencies yet they also reveal gaps in implementation, infrastructure provision, and targeted guidance for scaling virtual training modalities. The confluence of survey insights and policy review thus highlights not only the alignment between policy aspirations and institutional needs, but also the critical need for focused investment, clearer operational frameworks, and strengthened capacity development to fully realize Virtual TVET's potential across Myanmar's TVET ecosystem.

5. CONCLUSION

The study emphasizes that Virtual TVET for renewable energy systems in Myanmar is a promising but nascent approach to workforce development in the country. The survey findings indicate that the most significant skills gaps among learners are in technical and industry-specific competencies, alongside digital/ICT and soft skills (ILO, 2021; IRENA, 2021). The integration of digital learning modules, such as digital TVET frameworks, blended learning, and competency-based LMS delivery, demonstrates that institutions are actively leveraging virtual tools to enhance practical training despite infrastructural constraints. Innovative practices such as virtual workshops, simulations, digital assessments, and industry mentorships further emphasize the institutional efforts to strengthen learner competencies in renewable energy systems.

However, the adoption of Virtual TVET faces persistent challenges. Limited and unreliable internet connectivity, insufficient access to devices, and inadequate LMS knowledge among trainers were reported by a majority of respondents. These barriers, coupled with weak learner engagement and regulatory limitations, highlight the uneven adoption and scalability of virtual training initiatives across Myanmar.

The policy review reveals that Myanmar's National Education Law (2014) and the National Education Strategic Plan (2016-2021) provide a supportive framework for the modernization of TVET and the integration of digital technologies. International assessments, such as the OECD Multi-dimensional Review (2015), further emphasize the importance of aligning skills development with labour market demands. However, gaps remain in practical implementation, including limited infrastructure, inconsistent teacher capacity, and insufficient alignment of renewable energy programs with national energy priorities. These findings indicate that Virtual TVET can significantly enhance access to technical training, foster digital competencies, and promote sustainable energy practices. To realize its full potential, interventions should focus on:

- Expanding digital infrastructure and ensuring reliable connectivity in all regions.
- Strengthening teacher and trainer capacities in digital pedagogy and virtual tools.

- Encouraging stronger collaboration between TVET institutions and industry partners.
- Aligning Virtual TVET curricula with national renewable energy policies and international best practices.

In conclusion, while Virtual TVET is not yet a fully institutionalized solution, it presents a viable and adaptable strategy to address Myanmar's renewable energy workforce needs. The case study provides valuable insights into practical challenges, opportunities for scaling, and policy interventions that can guide future efforts to develop a skilled, digitally competent workforce capable of supporting the country's energy transition and broader sustainable development goals.

6. REFERENCES

Academic & Published Sources

Asian Development Bank. (2015). *Myanmar energy sector assessment, strategy, and road map*. Asian Development Bank.

Asian Development Bank. (2021). *Digital transformation in technical and vocational education and training in Asia and the Pacific*. Asian Development Bank.

International Energy Agency. (2021). *Net zero by 2050: A roadmap for the global energy sector*. IEA.

International Labour Organization. (2014). *Assessment study of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) in Myanmar*. ILO Asia-Pacific Working Paper Series.

International Labour Organization. (2021). *Skills development in the time of COVID-19: Taking stock of the initial responses in technical and vocational education and training*. ILO.

International Renewable Energy Agency. (2021). *Skills development for the energy transition: Preparing the workforce for renewable energy*. IRENA.

International Renewable Energy Agency. (2022). *Renewable energy and jobs: Annual review 2022*. IRENA.

Ministry of Education, Republic of the Union of Myanmar. (2016). *National Education Strategic Plan 2016–2021*. Ministry of Education.

Republic of the Union of Myanmar. (2014). *National Education Law*.

Tun, M. M. (2019). An overview of renewable energy sources and their energy potential for sustainable development in Myanmar. *European Journal of Sustainable Development Research*, 3(1), Article em0071. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejosdr/5737>

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (2020). *Technical and vocational education and training in the time of COVID-19: Challenges, opportunities, and responses*. UNESCO.

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (2021). *Reimagining our futures together: A new social contract for education*. UNESCO.

UNESCO-UNEVOC International Centre for Technical and Vocational Education and Training. (2018). *Transforming TVET in Myanmar*. UNESCO-UNEVOC.

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. (2015). *Paris Agreement*. UNFCCC.

Vakulchuk, R., Kresnawan, M. R., Overland, I., & Westphal, K. (2017). Myanmar's energy sector: Renewable energy potential and policy landscape. *Energy Policy*, 107, 273–283.

World Bank. (2015). *Myanmar national electrification project*. World Bank.

World Bank. (2020). *Remote learning and digital transformation in education systems*. World Bank.

Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case study research and applications: Design and methods* (6th ed.). SAGE Publications.

Online/Contextual Web Sources

ASEAN Centre for Energy. (2020). *Renewable energy development in Southeast Asia*.
<https://aseanenergy.org>

Borgen Project. (n.d.). Renewable energy in Myanmar.
<https://borgenproject.org/renewable-energy-in-myanmar/>

CEEED Philippines. (2025). COP30 Southeast Asian groups demand people-centered response to the climate crisis, end to fossil fuel expansion.
<https://ceedphilippines.com/cop30-southeast-asian-groups-demand-people-centered-response-to-the-climate-crisis-end-to-fossil-fuel-expansion/>

Council on Foreign Relations. (n.d.). Timeline: United Nations climate talks.
<https://www.cfr.org/timelines/un-climate-talks>

European Commission. (2023). Press corner: EU climate policies and COP outcomes.
https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_6591

European Commission. (2025). What did COP30 achieve?
https://climate.ec.europa.eu/news-other-reads/news/what-did-cop30-achieve-2025-12-01_en

International Institute for Sustainable Development. (2025). Insight: COP30 outcome — what it means and what's next. <https://www.iisd.org/articles/insight/cop-30-outcome-what-it-means-and-whats-next>

UNESCO-UNEVOC International Centre for TVET. (2018). *Transforming TVET in Myanmar [Country profile]*. <https://unevoc.unesco.org/home/MYANMAR%2B2018%2BTVET>